

The Perils of "Regional Perspective"

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This essay builds on an earlier article, in which I argued that the study of contentious politics in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) has been constricted by research agendas and theoretical paradigms drawn primarily from the Global North (El Mahdi 2024). Prior to 2011, our discipline's research agenda focused on different manifestations of elite-led politics, such as democratic transitions, regime change, and political Islam, at the expense of attuning to other forms of informal and mass political phenomenon which transpired into the uprisings that swept the MENA. Once the uprisings known as the Arab Spring unfolded, most of the new literature tried to straitjacket the biggest and most unprecedented cycles of contention into pre-existing categories and typologies, such as frameworks of democratic regime transitions or social movements theory. Rather than taking the opportunity to understand these unravelling events, innovative and dynamic as they were, most scholars were quick to jump to conclusions, establish casualties, and to encase regional countries into a contentious politics literature predominantly informed by experiences of the global-North (see also Kurzman 2012a). I concluded that, as such, our discipline continues to forgo opportunities to contribute to a broader understanding of significant political phenomena

in our region, as much as it misses the chance to open new theoretical frontiers.

Building off this argument, this essay underscores two related elements. First, the disconnect between the dynamic politics of the region and how they are interrogated by political science reflects broader disciplinary shortcomings. Mainstream political science work has systematically marginalized reflexive and critical approaches within both Western (specifically Anglophone) and regional (e.g., Middle East-based) scholarship. Second, construing this schism—between the politics of the region and how they are (re) presented and analyzed in orthodox political science scholarship—as one between “local” or “regional” versus “Western” perspectives tends to underestimate the ability of empire to universalize knowledge. This, in turn, encourages unwanted essentialization and tokenism of MENA scholars, and separates local spheres of research from Western academic circles through unequal power dynamics. Thus, juxtaposing a regional perspective against a Western one, which is increasingly echoed in conversations within our profession, miscalculates the far-reaching diffusion and hegemony of Euro-American paradigms in academia and elsewhere.

Do Regional Perspectives Reflect Local Priorities?

Many Western political scientists have long critiqued Euro-American-centric approaches to studying the MENA (e.g. Anderson 2006; Mitchell 2004; Wedeen 2016). These critiques—coupled with the conception of regional scholarship as an alternative site(s) in which these Euro-American-centric visions could be denaturalized, decentered, and provincialized—gave impetus to the idea of the “regional perspective” as an antidote to the Western one.¹ Notwithstanding its homogenizing tendency, this idea rests mainly on two interrelated assumptions: (1) Enough scholars in the region have their “own” research agendas which are different from their peers in the West; and (2) Regional scholarship is more reflexive and reflective of “local” priorities than its Western counterpart.

In their thorough survey of MENA-related articles in English-language political science journals over two decades, Cammett and Kendall (2021) make the distinction between the research priorities of regional scholars versus those of their Western counterparts. They conclude that “what is published on the Middle East in the most-cited journals in the profession may not always reflect the priorities of scholars and of citizens in the region” (Cammett and Kendall 2021, 455). Rather, “the highest-growth topics may reflect in part the priorities of Western researchers and agencies” (Cammett and Kendall 2021, 454). They concede their conclusions need further research, but their distinctions echo that geographic schism between two separate perspectives—that of the Western approach versus the local or regional agenda, the latter being portrayed as more authentic and indig-

enous to the Middle East.

The problem is that while this distinction is necessary to delineate the unequal power and resources that different academic communities possess, it does not necessarily mean these sides have truly different research programs. For example, within the literature on contentious politics in the Middle East that emerged following the 2011-12 Arab uprisings, the diversity of perspectives does not neatly correspond with geographic location. Many refreshingly critical perspectives have been championed by Western scholars based far outside the region, and who are not native speakers of any regional language (e.g. Lust 2013; Chalcraft 2016; Kurzman 2012b; Brown 2016).

Conversely, some of the most uncritical applications of Western-centric scholarly theories—such as studies that explained the Arab Spring through theories of democratic transitions or models of social revolutions, or which framed “the youth” as a unitary actor driven from Mannheim’s (1952) theory of generations—pervaded academic debates within and among political scientists within the Middle East, who in turn spread such approaches through their editorial columns, media programs, and other public engagements in their respective countries. The late Alfred Stepan felt justified upon his first visit to the region amidst the uprisings to pontificate to Tunisians and Egyptians about their chances for a democracy (2011). But similarly, many of these countries’ own elite—including locally-based political scientists—did something similar, for their pontifications were equally disconnected from the vantage point of local publics and ordinary people (see further Abo El-Gheit 2011).

¹ This thinking builds off Edward Said (1978, 1997). See, for example, Szanton (2004) and Miyoshi and Harootunian (2002).

Why Not?

Contrasting the regional versus Western perspectives in political science as diametric opposites, akin to a “thesis-antithesis” framework, misses a number of problems. It underestimates the impact of the Western academy as a colonial project shaping knowledge and its subjects, and which commands immense power to decide which ideas are valuable and worthy of diffusion throughout the world. This is a system where “the unspoken politics of theory... supposedly speaking on behalf of some universal and objective standard” determines “which scholarship could be regarded as theory, and which relegated to more subjective and parochial forms of knowledge” (Goh 2011, 2). The life trajectory of many Middle East-based academics is bound by not just the bodies of knowledge that Western circles hold dear, but also Western-based institutions and norms: graduate training, publishing opportunities, journal rankings, professional conferences, grant-seeking, and even the tenure and promotion systems of their universities. Even if the “local” scholar is not directly tied to this system, they are still immersed in Western paradigms, literatures, and networks reflecting its presence. In this way, the regional perspectives in the MENA championed by some Western critics as being more authentic or real are embedded in the very epistemology of Euro-American knowledge that gave rise to that Western criticism in the first place.

Another problem is that Middle East-based scholarship hardly constitutes a monolith of knowledge, distinguished more by what it is “not” (e.g., Western) than what it is. In reality, the diversity and criticality of scholarly perspectives from our region hinges on many more factors: the questions being asked, the methodologies being used, and the position-

ality of scholars themselves, in which geographic location is only one of many constituent parts. Gender, class, political affiliations, and other factors influence and differentiate social science scholarship in the MENA.

Thus, it is fallacy to assume that regional scholars—by virtue of being physically present in “the field” and possessing a comparative linguistic advantage—will automatically pursue research agendas that more closely reflect the priorities of fellow citizens, or more accurately interpret problems on the ground. Some political scientists in the MENA would find it difficult to navigate spaces or capture the subtleties of subtexts outside of their respective capital cities or even certain neighborhoods due to their gender or class. Others would miss any subtext altogether because of the methodology they choose to employ.

In a wider sense, while individual research agendas across the Middle East are (like elsewhere) subject to varying systems of academic incentives, they can resemble the Western academy in not easily accounting for, or valuing, relevance to local publics. Common imperatives conveyed to regional scholars include thinking about “gaps in the literature,” the inherent novelty of their argument or research finding, and the strategic value of a particular publication to one’s career—but not whether, for instance, their research pursues puzzles that resonate with the communities in which they work. The lack of academic freedom, scarcer funding opportunities, and many other limitations also play a role in circumscribing local research programs.

The Disciplinary Prism

Rather than focusing on demarcating Middle East perspectives to integrate into Western political science, it might be more useful to

address the core limitations of the discipline itself. In 2011, the APSA report *Political Science in the 21st Century* concluded that the discipline had been “ill equipped to develop explanations for the social, political, and economic processes that lead to groups’ marginalization,” and that this “limits the extent to which political science is relevant to broader social and political discourse” (APSA 2011, 1). The taskforce offered two explanations for such limitation: its analytical categories and its principal methods for study. More recently, the editors of the *American Political Science Review* (APSR), one of the flagship journals of the discipline, further acknowledged “concerns voiced by... political scientists who ask questions that our discipline often ignores and scholars who adopt approaches, epistemologies, and methods that fall outside what traditionally has been considered mainstream” (APSR 2023, 4). Whether from the MENA region or derived from Western institutions, reflexive work of all kinds regardless of origin will continue to be marginalized as long as the methodological and theoretical parameters defining what constitutes “good” (e.g., rigorous, scientific, reproducible, robust) research persist.

In two decades, the uptick in MENA-related articles published in the leading Western political science journals reflected a growing concern with “core disciplinary debates and its methods” (Cammett and Kendall 2021, 454). Thus, the problem is not only including MENA-based voices into the disciplinary apparatus of political science, but rather disentangling what being *local* means—and on what terms are they included. Truly critical views, approaches, and research from our region cannot overcome, let alone counter-balance, disciplinary limitations no matter how ground-breaking they may seem to be. Rather, they are relegated to being “localized

perspectives” only to be further peripheralized.

Without addressing disciplinary shortcomings, Middle East political science will continue along its current trajectory. It will bifurcate between a mainstream “doing business as usual” approach that hopes to fit into the defined boundaries and parameters of existing scholarship, or it will be heralded as marginalized critical scholarship used as a token of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) when needed. In the latter, Western scholars will continue citing regional work whenever they simply need to supplement their own theorization. Scholars from the region will continue to be invited to panels, committees, and even joint-research, as a symbol of inclusion but without being able to change course. ♦

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